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اُردو اسٹڈیز

(ذولسانی کتابی سلسلہ ۱)

۲۰۱۹

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URDU STUDIES

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RAJA GIDH: BREAKING GENDER STEREOTYPES

Arshad Masood Hashmi

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Seduction by religious leaders and therapists, Peter Rutter propounds in his book, *Sex in the Forbidden Zone: When Men in Power—Therapists, Doctors, Clergy, Teachers, and Others—Betray Women's Trust*, is especially easy when a psychologically-vulnerable woman confuses her emerging passion for life with her passion for sex. He further admonishes that once a relationship has entered the forbidden zone, it is unlikely that it will ever become a sex-free relationship again. Marie M. Fortune has discussed and disseminated the affairs in a church where a minister (one may include some self-made Indian godmen too) who happened to be a charismatic, spiritual person, knew the evil art of manipulating the women into bed with him because they were under his spell as their minister. There were different situations that compelled women to gratify his sexual demands. Fortune talks about a woman in a vulnerable state because of the death of her husband who was seduced by the minister on the pretext that sex with him would be a part of the healing process. She describes that minister as a

romantic/sexual predator in her book, *Is Nothing Sacred? When Sex Invades the Pastoral Relationship*.

The protagonist of the Urdu novel *Raja Gidh* [The King Scavenger] written by Bano Qudsiya (November 28, 1928 – February 04, 2017) resembles a *tantric* and ministerial healer who victimizes/seduces those women who are, somehow or the other, in a vulnerable state. Qaiyyum is a symbol of male chauvinism and hypocrisy, a self-deluding, jealous zealot, and beaten-up youth who seduces Seemi Shah, a desperately lonely girl who survives to become a victim after losing her love. Its implications are so grave that she eventually turns into a victim of revenge, rebellion and seduction. Written during the years of turmoil and nationwide demonstrations against the infamous *Hudood Ordinance 1979*, this novel presents a mockery of the system, of the State's and right wing's tightening grip on women. While on the one hand, some Pakistani women belonging to elite class were at war with the state, the religious hypocrisy was giving a free hand to males in using women as an object of sex and humiliation. Disappointed with the generation gap, cultural hegemony and predominant policies and processes to marginalize women, the novelist makes us feel the riot in her blood. Notwithstanding the prevalence of the legitimate male system of value, Qudsiya's deliberations on the lawful and unlawful in Islam, and her discourse on genetic mutation based on the concept of Good and Evil in Islam are the result of that powerlessness which emanates from the endless division of self by the outer forces. Her arguments favour the Islamic, and now, national system of piety wherefore the narrative and storyline of this novel mock the *Hudood Ordinance* and male's sanctions on female body and mind.

The much discussed character of this novel, Raja Gidh, who faces a trial at the International Conference of the Birds in the parallel narrative of the novel, is loathed by all the other birds because its community has assimilated itself with human

beings. The narrator compares scavengers with human beings and rightly and insightfully so discusses the lawful and the unlawful in Islam. But this deliberate incorporation of the Islamic ethics which has been used to expel scavengers from the bird community turns into an extreme illustration of paradox in the characterization of Qayyum, Suhail, Seemi and Abeda. Amtal's entry in Qayyum's life and sudden arrival of Aftab with his abnormal son do not add much to the story of this novel. Qudsiya would have conveyed her message powerfully even without their presence.

Seemi's interest in Aftab and later in Qayyum might be the result of the lack of love and affection from her parents, as indicated by the author; however one cannot deny soliciting her desire of elevation of the libratory aspirations when she offers her body to Qayyum in the Lawrence Garden. It is the Lahore of 1980/1981, and they regularly have sex in that garden. She tries to find solace in his arms. The garden becomes a meeting ground of the personal and the universal. When they had their first sexual relationship, the otherwise desperate and almost mad girl, filled with self-pity, Seemi Shah, smiles and asks Qayyum to leave the garden, playfully saying, "Naughty boy, police arrest them who are caught involved in shoddy activities. This [*our activity*] is also considered a breach of peace" (1981, p.122). Rutter construes that sometimes women are also seductive. There is a moment in the novel when Seemi asks Qayyum whether he finds her sexually frustrated (1981, p. 46). Qayyum says that she smiled while uttering these words and the seducer within him thinks that it was a smile filled with sorrow. To him, Seemi was more vulnerable now; and for Seemi, it was the beginning of her retributions, her revenge on her ex. The reader is made to believe that Seemi's surrender and her melting under the touch of Qayyum is an exercise in vain to feel Aftab through him, and simultaneously, this relationship of the seducer and the seduced leads to melancholy, madness, physical death of Seemi and moral decay of Qayyum.

She despises and abhors her ambitious parents because they are more indulged in themselves, in building their fortunes and in treading on the ways that would keep them, at least, look younger. Drawing a wall of detachment between parents and children, Qudisia seems to convey that these two generations of Pakistan are so involved in their own worlds that they cannot trust each other in any personal matter. Seemi's discussion with Qayyum also indicates that her parents have a queer sexual life too. By asking Qayyum whether she is sexually frustrated, she indirectly invites him to explore her body. She becomes a symbol of reactionary attitude in the context of the ethics of faithfulness, and laws of the land. Qudisia's disturbing and truly dark humor very skillfully projects the horribly grim reality and ugliness of modern city life of the youths who have been cut off from their roots. Seemi is unable to resist the sexual temptation. Throughout the discourses on Good and Evil there is a conspiracy of silence, a burning furnace of reactions and rebellion that wouldn't allow the author to approve the religious sanctions on her mind and body. Otherwise, she wouldn't have expounded that men have a discreet but very old relation with the *hunger* of women. She insinuates that when a man falls in love with a woman, he gets used to her hunger too. The new generation of "modern girl" has come to realize the secret that "expression of hunger conveys this message to a man that her being hungry is an indication of her not being inferior to men in her sexual hunger" (1981, p. 34).

What the author didn't dare telling is that why a girl/woman would demonstrate her *hunger* to a man! Very much like Professor von X. of Virginia Woolf's *A Room of One's Own*, some emotions make her jab her pen on the paper as if she were killing some noxious insect but even when she had killed it that did not satisfy her; she goes on killing it. She discovers to her chagrin that she cannot repress that flow of emotions in a young girl or in a married woman as in the case of Abeda. She lets the emotions boil and erupt besides her discourse on propagating religious ethics.

A Rawalpindi based author, Hammad Mushtaq, has treated this novel as a romantic writing. He is of the opinion that the novel relates the story of the unfulfilled love of Seemi and Qayyum who remain under the influence of a deep melancholy and a sense of nostalgia while the deeper meaning of the novel suggest the theme of *Halaal* [the lawful] and *Haraam* [the unlawful] (Mushtaq, 2012). This is what the novelist herself has propagated on different occasions. It is hard to consider it a love story because the tandems of love wither away with the death of Aftab in the beginning of the narrative itself. I see such statements as a departure from the truth. This novel could have never been survived in Zia-ul Haq's Pakistan without a forced and intentional inculcation of submission to the religious dictates of the state. I would like to draw the readers' attention to the argument of the Nightingale during the trial of the King Scavenger in the jungle. It forcefully argues that one should trace out the secret of the scavengers' insanity in the fall of man because...all forms of energy of human being are hidden in his sexual power. Unlike animals and birds, he doesn't use his sexuality to beget offspring, albeit, keeps that dark stallion of power pressed between his thighs. Later on, this galloping stallion helps him in attaining the distances of the world and heaven. If a man keeps his thighs wrapped tightly around that stallion, he achieves wisdom; if he loosens the grip then he falls down in frenzy, and thenceforth, is called a madman (1981, p.24).

Whole narrative of the novel revolves around this idea and the author is at pains in creating an atmosphere to contradict her primary plot. The portrayal of the lives of Qayyum and Seemi is done with great psychological depth. Narrated most often from the first-person viewpoint, the inherent message remains clear, coherent and compelling- sex is a taboo, premarital and extramarital affairs are a taboo, it is against the religious beliefs, it is against the moral values, but it is hard to escape the temptation even if one faces exclusion. Ironically, in the social fabric of Pakistan, the Raja Gidhs were not facing trials or expulsions, however, the ones they made

their prey were awarded punishments. A Pakistani female author, Shabnam Ashai, remarks that since his expulsion from Heaven, Adam is in torments, and he is continuously looking for the ways to get his wounds healed. Raja Gidh is a symbol of those wounded men. Another Pakistan born scholar, Masood Ahraf Raja, observes this novel as a discourse on articulating Muslim nationhood in Pakistan (Raja, 2007). His readings are based on the secondary narrative plot of the novel. I doubt the authenticity of this observation as well on the ground that most of the arguments in the parallel narrative discuss the psychodynamics of sexuality. His argument stands on a weaker premise as there are sufficient points of departure in the novel that demonstrate its characters as guilty of moral failures that make their victimization complete and irrevocable.

Controversy has always surrounded the novel's loosely knit plots but the message that it spreads cannot be underestimated by any critic or reader. In the hallucinatory tale of love/lovelessness, revenge and rebellion, she aptly portrays greedy first generation, unsatisfied younger generation that seeks real love but in vain and falls prey to its own ambitions. This tendency is a brutal truth because relations are without faith, trust and commitment. Usually, Bano Qudsia's writings involve a subtle mixture of inconsistencies. She loathes the institution of marriage and considers it nothing but an agreement to beget offspring. One of her writings, *Azadi-e-NiswaaN* ([Women's Liberation], *Nuqoosh*: Lahore, 122, 1977. Pp- 126-146), published couples of years before the appearance of this novel, deals in depth with the relation of man and woman. Realizing the fact that the new generation of Pakistani women are more interested in changing their standards with the help of Western education and Western living to stand equally beside men, she opines that the women of the second generation of Pakistan are striving hard to compete men educationally, financially and socially to live an independent life. Meanwhile, she stresses the need for a better understanding of women by men. She argues that the Pakistani males are mimicking the West in their pursuit of education and

material gains. Women, remaining behind the veils for fourteen centuries, have crossed the doorsteps of their home in this century. She also admits that some women, unconsciously apprehending the present ideals of men, have gone far away from the boundaries set by the society. She goes on to say that some women are victims of contradictions, and therefore, if they would accept their religion as standard of their life then their market value will be diminished. On the other hand, she also admits that the desire of seeking a man is hidden in the nature of a woman while the impact of inconsistency affects her whole life. In the same vein, drawing readers' attention to a woman's changing ideals, she says that the intelligent and educated girl of Pakistan does not trust that self-confident ideal. She, on the grounds of her education, seeks financial and sexual liberation, and, is all set to become a sexy Susan to please man. There is a clear indication of reaction against the male chauvinism and authoritarianism when she wonders whether a woman wants only to be moulded? Does she not nurture any of her own desire, ambition? Is she only a picture to be fixed in a man's frame (p. 130)? Interestingly, the same issue of *Nuqoosh* carries (1977, pp. 564-570) a biographical sketch of Qudsia by Parveen Atif in which Atif, a close associate of the novelist, writes that according to Qudsia, the fierce intensity of hue and cry in the society about sex is meaningless. It has uselessly kept sex hidden behind seven veils making it a forbidden tree- and the forbidden tree hidden behind seven veils throws the senses of pleasure into a burning furnace for no use. If an important part of the psyche of society is thrown into a fiery furnace then consequently nothing constructive would come out, she believes. Likewise, throughout the novel there is a fear of judgment, hatred, desperation, self-loathing, and confusion about one's self and the environment. It was not permissible to raise a voice against the system (read judiciary, male chauvinism) therefore *Raja Gidh* turned out to be a compassionate, comprehensive, and thoughtful treatment of an emerging problem of our time in Pakistan. The International Conference of the Birds (parallel narrative of the novel) is

defiant yet self-deluding act of retribution. Though it is a meet to discuss the psychopathic and sociopathic scavengers, it yields to a discourse on the forbidden zone where the primary narrative's characters love to dwell with all their temptations and perceptions based on reaction, rage, revenge and frustration.

Qayyum's sudden departure from Seemi and his seduction of Abeda to fulfill his carnal desires is also reactionary in its nature because he knew that Seemi was interested in him only due to his friendship with her ex. He ruled her body but he couldn't make her love him. Thus, Seemi while taking a revenge on Aftab and reacting against her "ambitious parents" used him as a medium to soothe her own libido. Qayyum's *tantric* musings to seduce Abeda and her eagerness to have extramarital relationship with him are also a perennial theme of revenge. They know that they are using each other, that they are victims of sexual betrayals and faithlessness. Qayyum (read Raja Gidh/ the King Scavenger/ the patriarchal system/ the male dominancy/ the male authoritarianism- whom no ordinance can prove guilty) is morbidly consumed by women, and wants to consume them. This is sheer madness, and madness is central to this novel. But, no one is being stoned!

Pakistan, as a nation and state, has been grappling since its creation with existential dilemma and the issue of national identity and the search for roots. The *salariat* (auxiliary class, a term coined by Hamza Alavi) has always been on the forefront of the religious and political affairs. The industrial elite, conservative merchant-trader class and landlords have always been socially and politically influential. They left no rooms for either political or social reforms; consequently, there was an adverse effect on younger generation in creating its consensus on the role of Islam as seen and presented by the new aristocracy, in the state. The postcolonial existence of this nascent country was threatened by its orthodox leadership. Despite being a pluralistic society, Pakistan used, misused and

abused the Islamic jurisprudence for the welfare of the ruling class and bureaucrats. There is a fierce resistance to change. Voyeuristically and sadistically, Qudsia represents that clash of existential crises in the form of the reactionary attitude of Qayyum, Seemi and Abeda. The contrasts of village and city life, science and holy people, sociology and ESP, Good and Evil, lawful and unlawful, and trust and betrayal symbolize existential paradoxes. Alienation, dispossession, loneliness, insanity and death are the ultimate results of living under a system that gives little thought to the individual freedom. Mocking the system, the self-centered characters of this novel dwell in their own delusions and fantasies. The novelist, being very well aware of the repercussions of loitering in the forbidden zone lets Abeda correct herself once she betrays her *majaazii Khuda* [earthly god] by seducing Qayyum, "...then I laid my hand pleadingly on the sacred tomb... don't know why Abeda got seated silently... she murmured, 'do tell me, are you not feeling pity for me'" (1981, p. 184).

It was sinister, troubling and disturbing for the author to openly and approvingly talk about the forbidden zone wounded up in a *cul-de-sac* by ignoring the phallus centric hysterics. That is the reason that the novel takes a forced new turn when by the end of the narration, the protagonist's bride, who was believed to be untouched, a virgin, is presented as a girl who is already pregnant. Qayyum is yet again alienated and an outsider. To the reader's utter dismay, no female character repents seducing or being seduced. It is the male protagonist, Raja Gidh, who is always despised and disgusted and, hitherto, has no value for appreciation of his own life.

The narratives, then, have real power!

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